

THE STUDY ON CRYSTALLIZATION OF PEEK-CARBON FIBER COMPOSITE

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Poly (ether-ether-ketone) (PEEK) is a semicrystalline thermoplastic with a crystallinity up to 48% and a glass transition at 145 C. The chemical structure of PEEK is

Since PEEK shows good mechanical properties, it is currently being studied as a high-performance plastic and as a matrix for fiber-reinforced composites [1,2]. For instance, aromatic polymer composites (APC), developed by Imperial Chemical Industries (ICI) of UK, are a new class of carbon fiber composite embedded by PEEK resin.

As a semicrystalline polymer, morphological features such as degree of crystallinity, spherulite size, crystallite orientation and interfacial structure in composites have a profound impact on the mechanical properties of polymers and their composites. These features are, in turn, affected by the variation in the processing conditions. To obtain a clear understanding of the processing-morphology-properties must be monitored so that critical processing parameters can be identified. Among morphological features, the interfacial structure is especially important for polymeric composites because the transverse tensile strength depends primarily on the interfacial strength between fiber and matrix [1].

In the literatures [2-6], it has been reported that the surface of carbon fiber affects on the crystallization and melt behaviors of PEEK, but the study on the interfacial structure is limited. In this paper the structure feature of a bunch of spherulite along the surface of carbon fiber has been clearly presented under the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) after PEEK-carbon fiber composite is etched by Ar plasma, and the crystallization rate of composite is faster than that of pure PEEK monitored by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) under the conditions of non- and isothermal crystallization. These experiment results are useful to further understand the interfacial structure of PEEK-carbon fiber composite and it affects on the properties of composite.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials used in the work was poly (ether-ether-ketone) (PEEK) resin and aromatic polymer composite (APC-2) supplied by ICI Co. Lid. The APC-2 consists of a matrix of PEEK reinforced with continuous, unidirectional carbon fiber. The pure PEEK resin was a film with a little yellow color, having a thickness of 100um. APC-2 sample was a black impregnated tape of carbon fiber with PEEK resin, having a thickness of 100um. The weight fraction of carbon fiber in APC-2 material determined by thermogravimetry was 66%. All the materials were pretreated in a vacuum oven at 50°C for 10 hrs.

Before observing the spherulite morphology of PEEK matrix in composite under scanning electron microscopy (SEM), APC-2 sample was heated to 400°C for 2 minutes to eliminate its thermal history and then rapidly cooled to crystallization temperature, 310°C. for 30 minutes for the melt crystallization, or quenched down to ice water and then rapidly heated to the crystallization temperature, 170°C, for 30 minutes for the rubbery crystallization. After crystallization under the conditions mentioned above, the APC-2 sample was etched by Ar plasma in the Eiko IB-3 ion coater, see Figure 1. The conditions of etching were 3 W for etching power and 20 to 40 minutes for etching time. After evaporating a thin layer of platinum on the etched surface of APC-2 sample, the morphology features of APC-2 sample were examined by Hitachi S-530 scanning electron microscopy operating at an accelerating voltage of 25 keV.

The crystallization process of PEEK resin and matrix of PEEK-carbon fiber composite (APC-2) under non- and isothermal crystallization conditions was investigated by a Perkin-Elmer DSC-2C using the same pretreatment methods previously used on morphology investigation for eliminating the thermal history. For isothermal crystallization, samples were rapidly cooled to the crystallization temperature (T_c) from melt or were first quenched down to ice water from melt and then were rapidly heated to the crystallization temperature (T_c) from rubbery state. Crystallization exotherms were monitored as a function of time at different T_c . For nonisothermal crystallization, the melt or rubbery state samples were crystallized at constant cooling or heating rate of 5, 10, 20, and 40°C/min. The crystallization exotherms in each run were measured as a function of time and temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Morphological features of PEEK-carbon fiber composite (APC-2)

Effect of the carbon fiber surface on the morphological features of PEEK matrix has been investigated by SEM. After PEEK-carbon fiber composite (APC-2) was etched by Ar plasma, the morphology of a bunch of spherulites along the carbon fiber surface has been presented in Figure 2. These two SEM micrographs in Figure 2 clearly show that no matter wherever crystallization from melt or rubbery state, the morphological feature of a bunch of spherulites along the carbon fiber surface have been formed, demonstrating that the carbon fiber surface acts as nucleation sites for crystallization of PEEK matrix.

PEEK's spherulites shown in Figure 2 for APC-2 sample have two features which are diagrammatically shown in Figure 3. Figure 3 (a) schematically shows an almost complete spherulite. It is very important to note that the characters of complete spherulites shown in SEM micrograph are that their center coincide with the axis line of carbon fiber and they grow along carbon fiber axis line with one after another. It is obvious that these spherulite are formed by induction nucleating carbon fiber surface. Figure 3(b) indicates an incomplete spherulite observed in Figure 2. The incomplete spherulite nucleates evidently coincide with the carbon fiber surface, so that it clearly and directly indicates that the forming of these incomplete spherulites is dependant upon the carbon fiber surface. It is indicated, therefore, that the surface of carbon fiber in APC-2 composite has very strong ability to induce PEEK matrix to crystallize. The reason that we can observe in and complete spherulites in SEM micrographs is that the carbon fiber is distributed on the different level. The two spherulites shown in Figure 2 are essentially a same spherulite induced by carbon fiber.

From the SEM micrographs it is clearly observed that PEEK spherulites in APC-2 composite grow in the way in which they make contact with carbon

fiber, so that finally forming spherulites are practically incomplete, it means that a part of them is truncated by carbon fiber and this spherulite is called as "truncated spherulite". It has been found in the literature [2] that the Avrami exponent, n , of APC-2 sample for crystallization process is smaller than that of pure PEEK resin. The decrease of Avrami exponent for PEEK matrix in APC-2 composite indicates on the certain degree that growth of spherulites is hindered [7].

The volume fraction of carbon fiber in APC-2 sample is about 60% and we find that the diameter of carbon fiber is about 8 μ m from Figure 2, so that there are a lot of nucleating carbon fiber surface in APC-2 sample for inducing crystallization of PEEK matrix. Comparing the two micrographs in Figure 2, it is found that almost all of spherulite nucleases coincide with the carbon fiber surface. This result shows that in crystallization process the nucleases of PEEK in composite are first formed in surface of carbon fiber and then grow continuously to form complete spherulites until adjacent spherulite collision. According to Keith and Padden [8], impurities and some macromolecules which cannot crystallize diffuse away from growing crystal surfaces. Therefore, the inducing nucleation of carbon fiber is dominant, impurities and these macromolecules will be accumulated at the spherulite-spherulite interface, shown in Figure 4, and the interfacial bond between fiber and PEEK matrix will be strong.

2. Effect of carbon fiber surface on crystallization process of PEEK matrix

The DSC scans in nonisothermal crystallization process for PEEK and APC-2 samples are shown in Figure 5 for cold crystallization and melt processes at heating rate of 20°C/min and for melt crystallization processes at cooling rate of 20°C/min. Upon heating at 20°C/min for PEEK and APC-2 samples, the glass transition temperature, T_g , at about 145°C, cold crystallization temperatures, $T_{c,h}$, at 180.5 and 179.6°C respectively, and melting point temperatures, T_m , at 338.8 and 344.6°C respectively, are found, see Figure 5 (a). Upon cooling at 20°C/min from melt, crystallization exotherms ($T_{c,c}$) at 283.3 and 290.0°C respectively for PEEK and APC-2 samples are shown in Figure 5(b). The results shown in Figure 5 indicate that $T_{c,h}$ for APC-2 is lower than $T_{c,h}$ for PEEK for crystallization from rubbery state, but $T_{c,c}$ for APC-2 is higher than $T_{c,c}$ for PEEK crystallization from melt. Figure 6 further shows the correlation between $T_{c,h}$ and heating rate, and between $T_{c,c}$ and cooling rate, for PEEK and APC-2 samples. It is obvious that in different rate $T_{c,h}$ for APC-2 are always lower than $T_{c,h}$ for PEEK, but $T_{c,c}$ for APC-2 are always higher than $T_{c,c}$ for PEEK, indicating the carbon fiber surface in APC-2 composite not only can induce PEEK matrix to crystallize, but also can accelerate crystallization rate of PEEK matrix upon nonisothermal crystallization process, so that $T_{c,h}$ is lowered from rubbery crystallization and $T_{c,c}$ is raised from melt crystallization for APC-2.

The crystallization of PEEK and APC-2 samples from melt or rubbery state under the isothermal crystallization conditions are also evidently different. Figure 7 shows the correlation between time in that maximum of heat flow is reached, t_{max} , and crystallization temperature, T_c , for PEEK and APC-2 samples. It is quite evident that t_{max} of APC-2 are smaller than t_{max} of PEEK in the same T_c no matter wherever isothermal crystallization from melt or rubbery state. This experiment result about isothermal crystallization demonstrates again that the surface of carbon fiber in APC-2 composite can induce PEEK matrix to crystallize, so that the crystallization rate of PEEK matrix is accelerated and t_{max} is decreased.

The experimental results of morphology and crystallization process of

PEEK and PEEK-carbon fiber composite all indicate that the surface of carbon fiber has strong ability to induce PEEK matrix to crystallize.

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Figure 1. Eiko IB-3 ion coater.

(a)

(b)

Fig.2. SEM micrographs of PEEK-carbon fiber composite.
 (a): Crystallization from melt, 310°C, 30 min;
 (b): Crystallization from rubbery state, 170°C, 30 min

(a)

(b)

Fig.3. Schematic diagrams of the two spherulite morphologies shown in SEM Micrographs.

Fig.4. Interfacial structure between spherulites in PEEK-carbon fiber composite.

Fig.5. Typical DSC thermograms of PEEK and APC-2: (a): amorphous polymer upon heating at 20°C/min; (b): cooling scan from melt at 20°C/min.

Fig.6. Plot of $T_{c,c}$ and $T_{c,h}$ versus cooling or heating rate for PEEK and APC-2 samples. (\square) and (Δ): PEEK; (\bullet) and (\circ): APC-2.

Fig.7. Plot of T_c versus t_{max} for isothermal crystallization from melt or from rubbery state of PEEK and APC-2 samples. (\square) and (\bullet): PEEK; (\circ) and (Δ): APC-2.